

**INSTRUCTIONAL SUPERVISORY PRACTICES OF SCHOOL HEADS AND
CLASSROOM INSTRUCTIONAL PRACTICES OF ELEMENTARY
SCHOOL TEACHERS IN ALABAT ISLAND,
DIVISION OF QUEZON**

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ABSTRACT

This study determined the instructional supervisory practices of school heads and classroom instructional practices of teachers in Alabat Island, Division of Quezon, utilizing a descriptive method. The researcher chose participants for the study using purposive sampling which involved 23 school heads and 255 teachers in Alabat Island, Division of Quezon. A research questionnaire assessed the level of school heads' instructional supervisory practices and teachers' classroom instructional practices using a 5-point Likert Scale. Thus, weighted mean was used to determine the level of instructional supervisory practices of school heads and classroom instructional practices of teachers. The results showed that school heads implemented instructional supervisory practices such as peer supervision, clinical supervision, developmental supervision, and differentiated supervision at a high level. Peer supervision received the lowest mean, indicating potential areas for improvement. Similarly, teachers' classroom instructional practices, including content knowledge and pedagogy, learning environment, curriculum and planning, and assessment and reporting, were highly practiced. However, the aspect of diversity of learners in teachers' classroom instructional practices obtained the lowest mean, indicating it as well-practiced. Moreover, spearman's rho analysis showed no significant relationship between school heads' instructional supervisory practices and teachers' classroom instructional practices, accepting the null hypothesis. Consequently, a capacity-building program was developed to enhance instructional effectiveness, targeting indicators with the lowest mean in both school heads' instructional supervisory practices and teachers' classroom instructional practices. Specifically, the program aims to improve teachers' capabilities in effectively catering to diverse student needs, particularly in the areas related to the diversity of learners.

Keywords: *instructional supervisory practices, classroom instructional practices, peer supervision, clinical supervision, developmental supervision, differentiated supervision, content knowledge and pedagogy, learning environment, curriculum and planning, assessment and reporting, diversity of learners*

INTRODUCTION

Education is a driving force for societal change, shaping the lives of individuals and contributing to overall progress. Students are the focal point of education, with research indicating that their development relies heavily on the skills and dedication of teachers. Moreover, the proficiency of stakeholders in instructional supervision, coupled with their collaboration with other stakeholders, significantly impacts the effectiveness of teachers. The effective execution of education relies on the collaborative efforts of all stakeholders, with instructional supervisors assuming a vital role in assisting teachers in facilitating student learning (Sumapal and Haramain, 2023).

Thus, providing instructional supervision to teachers is a critical responsibility of school administrators and a vital component of their supervisory practice. This instructional leadership involves establishing clear visions, setting high standards, supervising classroom instruction, managing resources, and cultivating stakeholders' relationships. When provided correctly, instructional feedback positively influences teachers' expertise and professional development (Balyer and Özcan, 2020). School administrators empower teachers to implement instructional practices that foster independent and strategic learning among students through effective instructional supervision.

Highly effective instructional strategies have a direct and profound impact on students' engagement, motivation, and academic accomplishments. When teaching approaches are meticulously aligned with recognized quality standards, they establish a steadfast and demanding learning environment accessible to all students. This alignment ensures that instructional methodologies, materials, and assessments are intricately designed to cater to the unique needs of diverse learners and actively foster their academic progression (Meng, 2023).

Consequently, Sumapal and Haramain (2023) highlighted the interconnectedness between instructional supervision and teachers' guidance, emphasizing how they support and enhance the teaching and learning process. Instructional supervision is essential, especially for teachers at varying experience levels who may need assistance in honing their practical teaching skills. Supervisory practices play a vital role in ensuring quality education and improving student performance. Effective teaching requires professional competence, and supervisors should guide, support, and evaluate. While emphasizing instructional leadership, school heads often assume additional responsibilities, such as maintaining discipline.

Buagas and Ching (2023) concluded that school administrators significantly contribute to improving instruction and the teaching-learning process through effective supervision. They prioritize recognizing teachers' strengths and needs to foster growth in a supportive environment, promoting collegial relationships among teachers and instructional leaders. Their supervisory methods prioritize trust, integrity, and mutual respect while emphasizing the effective allocation of resources to enhance instructional skills.

On the other hand, Baggay et al. (2021) emphasized that the role of a teacher has always been crucial in shaping the world's future. The ideas that will bring forth a new world lie within their teaching. Given the current state of education, teaching has become more challenging. Therefore, it's crucial to prioritize the well-being of our teachers to ensure a positive future direction.

Nevertheless, teachers are crucial to the success of the educational process in schools, as they are responsible for cultivating well-educated students. Thus, teachers need to be both well-trained and initiative-taking, as this directly impacts their performance. However, it is important to note that teachers operate within the guidance of school heads and are not entirely independent in their roles (Ahmed et al., 2021).

However, according to Akrong (2021), school heads frequently lack proper training for their supervisory roles, resulting in the reliance on trial-and-error methods. This leads to challenges such as inconsistent organization of instructional supervision and difficulties in adhering to planned supervisory activities throughout the academic year.

Hence, while the intensity of instructional supervision is crucial, adherence to correct principles is paramount. The behavior of supervisors should mirror professional standards, thereby influencing the quality of teaching by teachers (Maisyaroh et al., 2021).

Unfortunately, through surveys, interviews, and observations, the researcher discovered that teachers who received comprehensive feedback and technical assistance during their performance evaluations showed improvement in their classroom instructional practices, contrasting with minimal feedback recipients who demonstrated little to no progress. This significant finding underscores the critical role of effective feedback in shaping teaching quality, a point corroborated by Balyer and Özcan (2020), who highlight its importance for teachers' professional development and classroom effectiveness. Therefore, this scenario prompted the researcher to conduct the study to uncover the gaps and relationships between the instructional supervisory practices of school heads and the classroom instructional practices of teachers.

Research Questions

This research determined the instructional supervisory practices of school heads and classroom instructional practices of elementary school teachers in Alabat Island, Division of Quezon.

Specifically, this study seeks to answer the following questions:

1. What is the level of instructional supervisory practices implemented by school heads in Alabat Island in terms of:
 - 1.1 peer supervision;
 - 1.2 clinical supervision;
 - 1.3 developmental supervision;
 - 1.4 differentiated supervision?

2. What is the level of classroom instructional practices of elementary school teachers in Alabat Island in terms of the following domains:
 - 2.1 content knowledge and pedagogy;
 - 2.2 learning environment;
 - 2.3 diversity of learners;
 - 2.4 curriculum and planning;
 - 2.5 assessment and reporting?

3. Is there a significant relationship between the level of instructional supervisory practices of school heads and classroom instructional practices of elementary school teachers in Alabat Island?

4. What capacity-building program could be introduced based on the findings of the study?

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

The researcher utilized a descriptive research method, which entails recording, describing, interpreting, analyzing, and comparing events. It involves observing and documenting phenomena without manipulating variables. The objective is to accurately portray a situation or event using methods such as surveys or observations, without making conclusions regarding cause and effect. It clarifies the current characteristics or states of subjects in their natural settings. The researcher used this method to identify the different instructional supervisory practices of school heads and classroom instructional practices of elementary school teachers in Alabat Island.

Research Locale

The researcher conducted the study on Alabat Island in Quezon Province. The researcher is one of the teachers in Alabat Island, wherein she found out that most of the schools did not meet the division target of 75% MPS in all learning areas, as reflected in the Division Monitoring and Evaluation Plan Adjustment (DMEPA). The identified need for intervention prompted the researcher to conduct the study in the locale.

Alabat Island is part of the Philippine archipelago, lies in the Province of Quezon, CALABARZON region, positioned along the eastern coast of Southern Luzon. Covering an area of 192 square kilometers, it is home to a population of 41,822 people. The island consists of three municipalities: Perez on the northern tip, Alabat town proper in the center, and Quezon in the south.

Perez District encompasses six (6) public elementary schools and one (1) integrated school, while Alabat District comprises two (2) public elementary schools and three (3) integrated schools. Additionally, the Quezon District comprises eleven (11) public elementary schools. Therefore, Alabat Island consists of nineteen (19) elementary schools, six (6) secondary schools, and four (4) integrated schools.

Research Population and Sample

The researcher chose participants for the study using purposive sampling. This method is not random and does not require specific theories or a fixed number of participants. Instead, the researcher identifies what information is needed and seeks out individuals with relevant knowledge or experience willing to provide it. The study utilized twenty-three (23) school heads and two hundred fifty-five (255) elementary school teachers in Alabat Island.

The population of the study indicates that there are a total of twenty-three school heads in the public elementary schools. However, the researcher was only able to retrieve data for eighteen of them. Similarly, while there are 255 elementary school teachers in total, data was only retrieved for 214, as some elementary school teachers declined to participate due to various reasons. Some respondents mentioned their busy schedules and overwhelming workload. Consequently, they expressed their inability to allocate time to respond to the questionnaire due to the pressing nature of their responsibilities.

Research Instrument

The researcher used a questionnaire created for the study and validated by experts in the field. The survey instrument served as the primary tool for gathering reliable and primary data. The instrument was answered separately by the school heads and elementary school teachers to avoid biased answers.

The questionnaire contains two sets of practices. The first set consists of the instructional supervisory practices of school heads, including peer supervision, clinical supervision, developmental supervision, and differentiated supervision. The first set, which consists of instructional supervisory practices of school heads, had been rated by the elementary school teachers. The indicators were rated by teachers using a 5-point Likert Scale. The second set is about the classroom instructional practices of elementary school teachers in terms of content knowledge and pedagogy, learning environment, diversity of learners, curriculum and planning, assessment and reporting. It includes indicators of dimensions adapted from the Classroom Observation Tool (COT) for proficient teachers. These indicators illustrate observable practices of teachers in the classroom, as rated by school heads.

Thus, the school heads allotted time to answer the questionnaire by rating the indicators adapted from the Classroom Observation Tool (COT) using a 5-Point Likert scale where five was the highest rating with corresponding description and descriptive interpretation. Furthermore, three (3) experts in the field, comprising Education Program Supervisors (EPS) from the Schools Division Office of Quezon Province, validated the researcher-made questionnaire.

Five-point Likert Scale for Instructional Supervisory Practices of School Heads

Scale	Mean Interval	Description	Descriptive Interpretation
5	4.20 – 5.00	Highly Practiced	100% practiced
4	3.40 – 4.19	Well-Practiced	75-99% practiced
3	2.60 – 3.39	Moderately Practiced	50-74% practiced
2	1.80 – 2.59	Less Practiced	25-49% practiced
1	1.00 – 1.79	Almost Not Practiced	0-24% practiced

Five-point Likert Scale for Classroom Instructional Practices of Elementary School Teachers

Scale	Mean Interval	Description	Descriptive Interpretation
5	4.20 – 5.00	Highly Practiced	The teacher uses well-connected pedagogical aspects of the indicator to create an environment that addresses individual and group learning goals. (100% practiced)
4	3.40 – 4.19	Well-Practiced	The teacher uses well-connected pedagogical aspects of the indicator that consistently are aligned with student development and support students to be successful learners. (75-99% practiced)
3	2.60 – 3.39	Moderately Practiced	The teacher demonstrates a range of associated pedagogical aspects of the indicator that usually are aligned with the learners' developmental needs. (50-74% practiced)
2	1.80 – 2.59	Less Practiced	The teacher demonstrates a range of associated pedagogical aspects of the indicator that sometimes are aligned with the learners' developmental needs. (25-49% practiced)
1	1.00 – 1.79	Almost Not Practiced	The teacher demonstrates a limited range of loosely associated pedagogical aspects of the indicator. (0-24% practiced)

Data Gathering Procedure

The researcher sought approval from the Schools Division Superintendent of Division of Quezon for the letter requests to the concerned school heads and elementary school teachers. Then copies of these were reproduced for distribution. The reproduced copies were distributed personally to the identified respondents. An explanatory letter was also attached to the survey instrument, providing letter requests and basic instructions for filling out the instrument. Likewise, the researcher explained and gave instructions to the respondents for proper guidance in answering the instrument.

Statistical Treatment of Data

The relevance of any research undertaking depends upon the researcher's appropriate use of statistical treatment in analyzing and interpreting data. The statistical formula used includes the following:

Weighted mean was used to determine the level of instructional supervisory practices of school heads and classroom instructional practices of elementary school teachers in Alabat Island.

Spearman's rho was utilized to assess the relationship between the instructional supervisory practices of school head and classroom instructional practices of elementary school teachers in Alabat Island.

Scope and Delimitation of the Study

The researcher involved the twenty-three (23) school heads and two hundred fifty-five (255) proficient teachers (Teacher I-III) among the public elementary schools in Alabat Island in assessing the instructional supervisory practices of school heads and classroom instructional practices of elementary school teachers.

The study assessed the classroom instructional practices of proficient teachers, specifically those categorized as career stage 2 (Teacher I-III) according to the Philippine Professional Standards for Teachers (PPST). Proficient teachers exhibit autonomy in planning, executing, and overseeing learning tasks following curriculum and assessment guidelines. They actively engage in collaborative learning with colleagues and stakeholders to cultivate mutual development and consistently improve the competencies, skills, and methods of career stage 1 (Beginning Teachers).

RESULTS

PART I. Level of the Instructional Supervisory Practices of School Heads

Table 1.1

Level of the Instructional Supervisory Practices of School Heads in Alabat Island in terms of Peer Supervision as evaluated by the elementary school teachers

Indicators	Frequency					Mean	SD	DI
	5	4	3	2	1			
1. My school head develops professional relationships among peers that nurture integrity, openness, trust, and respect.	97	103	11	3	0	4.37	0.65	HP
2. My school head collaborates with other mentors, coaches, and practitioners to organize and conduct teacher capability building programs.	110	94	7	3	0	4.45	0.63	HP
3. My school head serves as resource speaker and or/ consultant in INSETs.	133	76	5	0	0	4.60	0.54	HP
4. My school head shares the best practices with his/her fellow instructional leaders regarding the development and implementation of school plans aligned with institutional goals and policies.	109	87	16	2	0	4.42	0.67	HP
5. My school head regularly attend trainings, seminars, and workshops to develop his/her knowledge and skills as an instructional leader.	130	74	9	1	0	4.56	0.60	HP
6. My school head shows his/her eagerness for professional development through pursuing his/her graduate studies.	95	100	15	4	0	4.34	0.69	HP
7. My school head serves as a panel in research plenums to give comments and suggestions to researchers.	71	82	52	8	1	4.00	0.88	WP
8. My school head includes community leaders in conducting staff meetings to improve professional interaction with the stakeholders.	118	78	14	4	0	4.45	0.70	HP
9. My school head raises the concerns and issues of our school to his/her superiors and fellow instructional leaders to seek sympathy and support in difficult situations.	114	81	15	4	0	4.43	0.71	HP
10. My school head taps the help of organizations to extend the support given to the learners.	118	85	9	2	0	4.49	0.63	HP
Composite Mean						4.41	0.67	HP
Legend:	4.20 – 5.00	<i>Highly Practiced (HP)</i>						
	3.40 – 4.19	<i>Well-Practiced (WP)</i>						
	2.60 – 3.39	<i>Moderately Practiced (MP)</i>						
	1.80 – 2.59	<i>Less Practiced (LP)</i>						
	1.00 – 1.79	<i>Almost Not Practiced (ANP)</i>						

Table 1.2

Level of the Instructional Supervisory Practices of School heads in Alabat Island with a focus on Clinical Supervision as evaluated by the elementary school teachers

Indicators	Frequency					Mean	SD	DI
	5	4	3	2	1			
1. My school head promotes the efficiency of classes through observations and visitations.	118	88	7	1	0	4.51	0.59	HP
2. My school head leads in the evaluation of learner's achievement and utilizes results to improve learning.	110	93	10	1	0	4.46	0.61	HP
3. My school head provides systematic assessment and constructive feedback to teachers about personal and professional strengths and needs.	94	109	10	1	0	4.38	0.60	HP
4. My school head assists teachers to reflect on personal teaching performance and strengthen professional identity through careful analysis.	101	102	10	1	0	4.42	0.61	HP
5. My school head undertakes instructional goals to comprehensively explain the use of pedagogy to teachers for better learning outcomes.	98	106	8	2	0	4.40	0.61	HP
6. My school head utilizes procedures that promote collaboration, mutual trust, and open communication.	102	95	15	2	0	4.39	0.66	HP
7. My school head fosters open and continuous deliberation on curriculum issues and problems by connecting practice and theory.	96	110	6	2	0	4.40	0.60	HP
8. My school head promotes programs and projects of DepEd to improve teaching and learning.	122	83	8	1	0	4.52	0.59	HP
9. My school head encourages teachers to inquire on good practices and pursue better alternatives for the improvement of teaching and learning.	124	83	6	1	0	4.54	0.58	HP
10. My school head regularly provides professional, technical and instructional assistance to teachers.	111	93	9	1	0	4.47	0.60	HP
Composite Mean						4.45	0.60	HP
Legend:	4.20 – 5.00	<i>Highly Practiced (HP)</i>						
	3.40 – 4.19	<i>Well-Practiced (WP)</i>						
	2.60 – 3.39	<i>Moderately Practiced (MP)</i>						
	1.80 – 2.59	<i>Less Practiced (LP)</i>						
	1.00 – 1.79	<i>Almost Not Practiced (ANP)</i>						

Table 1.3

Level of the Instructional Supervisory Practices of School heads in Alabat Island in terms of Developmental Supervision as evaluated by the elementary school teachers

Indicators	Frequency					Mean	SD	DI
	5	4	3	2	1			
1. My school head diagnoses our developmental needs based on our developmental plans in the IPCRF.	116	81	16	1	0	4.46	0.65	HP
2. My school head diagnoses our developmental levels, expertise, commitment, educational situation, and selects the interpersonal approach that creates the best supervision match.	109	92	11	2	0	4.44	0.64	HP
3. My school head uses the data collected through observation in identifying the learning gaps that will serve as a basis in developing interventions for teacher development.	107	96	10	1	0	4.44	0.61	HP
4. My school head encourages us to participate in teacher induction programs that promotes reflective practice, build instructional knowledge, and maximize student learning.	121	85	7	1	0	4.52	0.59	HP
5. My school head includes developmental programs in the School Improvement Plan (SIP) to improve classroom and school instruction by enabling teachers as life-long learner.	123	82	9	0	0	4.53	0.58	HP
6. My school head encourages us to participate in developmental programs like In-Service Trainings (INSET), seminars, and workshops to improve our classroom instructional practices.	139	71	4	0	0	4.63	0.52	HP
7. My school head provides developmental instructional models that aims to appropriately modify processes and address the dimensions of teaching and learning.	108	99	5	2	0	4.46	0.59	HP
8. My school head uses selected interpersonal approach to assist us in instructional problem solving.	110	95	8	1	0	4.47	0.59	HP
9. My school head strictly follows DepEd Orders/ Memoranda that aims for teacher development.	137	68	5	4	0	4.58	0.64	HP
10. My school head expresses confidence in my plans and ability to carry out any development on changes as the improvement plan progresses.	112	93	6	3	0	4.47	0.63	HP
Composite Mean						4.50	0.60	HP

Legend: 4.20 – 5.00 *Highly Practiced (HP)*
 3.40 – 4.19 *Well-Practiced (WP)*
 2.60 – 3.39 *Moderately Practiced (MP)*
 1.80 – 2.59 *Less Practiced (LP)*
 1.00 – 1.79 *Almost Not Practiced (ANP)*

Table 1.4

Level of the Instructional Supervisory Practices Implemented by School heads in Alabat Island in terms of Differentiated Supervision as evaluated by the elementary school teachers

Indicators	Frequency					Mean	SD	DI
	5	4	3	2	1			
1. My school head prepares instructional supervision plan that consists of mode of supervision, remarks, and technical assistance provided/needed to strengthen teacher's individual needs.	110	94	9	1	0	4.46	0.60	HP
2. My school head employs differentiated procedures for teacher's formative evaluation which are appropriate to respective levels of teacher's professional development.	99	103	10	2	0	4.40	0.63	HP
3. My school head considers the result of our Self-Assessment Tool (SAT) as a basis in crafting the instructional supervisory plan.	112	90	11	1	0	4.46	0.62	HP
4. My school head consistently monitors the quarterly performance of teachers and allots time for one on one consultation that aims to address teacher's individual problems/needs.	103	106	4	1	0	4.45	0.56	HP
5. My school head uses different approaches and allots one on one consultation in addressing teacher's individual problems/needs.	95	110	7	2	0	4.39	0.60	HP
6. My school head engages teachers in planning, designing, and evaluation of the individual professional development programs.	114	93	6	1	0	4.50	0.58	HP
7. My school head links developmental programs that caters teacher's individual needs.	103	104	6	1	0	4.44	0.58	HP
8. My school head involves teacher's in teacher evaluations, staff development, and informal observation to improve classroom instructional practices, with regards to experiences and competence.	106	105	3	0	0	4.48	0.53	HP
9. My school head uses evaluations to provide meaningful feedback to teachers based on teacher's individual needs and level of expertise.	97	109	6	2	0	4.41	0.60	HP
10. My school head regularly reviews teacher's Individual Performance Commitment and Review Form (IPCRF) to link individual achievements.	103	102	7	2	0	4.43	0.61	HP
Composite Mean						4.44	0.59	HP
Legend:	4.20 – 5.00	<i>Highly Practiced (HP)</i>						
	3.40 – 4.19	<i>Well-Practiced (WP)</i>						
	2.60 – 3.39	<i>Moderately Practiced (MP)</i>						
	1.80 – 2.59	<i>Less Practiced (LP)</i>						
	1.00 – 1.79	<i>Almost Not Practiced (ANP)</i>						

Table 1.5*Summary Table of the Instructional Supervisory Practices Implemented by School Heads*

Skills	Composite Mean	Verbal Interpretation
Peer Supervision	4.41	HP
Clinical Supervision	4.45	HP
Developmental Supervision	4.50	HP
Differentiated Supervision	4.44	HP
Grand Mean	4.45	HP

Legend: 4.20 – 5.00 *Highly Practiced (HP)*
3.40 – 4.19 *Well-Practiced (WP)*
2.60 – 3.39 *Moderately Practiced (MP)*
1.80 – 2.59 *Less Practiced (LP)*
1.00 – 1.79 *Almost Not Practiced (ANP)*

PART II. Level of Classroom Instructional Practices of Elementary School Teachers

Table 2.1

Level of Classroom Instructional Practices of Elementary School Teachers in terms of Content Knowledge and Pedagogy as observed by the School Heads

Indicators	Frequency					Mean	SD	DI
	5	4	3	2	1			
1. The teachers apply extensive knowledge of content beyond his/her area of specialization.	6	11	1	0	0	4.28	0.57	HP
2. The teachers motivate learners to investigate the teaching area to expand their knowledge and satisfy their curiosity.	6	11	1	0	0	4.28	0.57	HP
3. The teachers cite intra and interdisciplinary content relationships.	7	10	1	0	0	4.33	0.59	HP
4. The teachers demonstrate responsible use of online and multimedia platforms by applying digital etiquette and responsible social interaction.	6	10	1	0	1	4.11	0.96	WP
5. The teachers address issues, such as plagiarism, cyberbullying, copyright, and/or takes precaution in sharing sensitive information in the use of ICT-based learning materials and/or activities.	7	10	0	0	1	4.22	0.94	HP
6. The teachers employ activities that enhance and support learners' higher level of literacy and/or numeracy skills as a significant part of his/her instruction.	7	10	1	0	0	4.33	0.59	HP
7. The teachers give learners opportunities to compare ideas.	7	10	0	1	0	4.28	0.75	HP
8. The teachers give learners opportunities to synthesize or summarize information within or across disciplines.	7	10	0	1	0	4.28	0.75	HP
9. The teachers demonstrate a well-developed ability in using communication strategies, such as code switching and translation.	7	10	0	1	0	4.28	0.75	HP
10. The teachers establish classroom practices which promote open communication between the teacher and learners, and among the learners and their peers.	7	11	0	0	0	4.39	0.50	HP
Composite Mean						4.28	0.70	HP
Legend:	4.20 – 5.00	<i>Highly Practiced (HP)</i>						
	3.40 – 4.19	<i>Well-Practiced (WP)</i>						
	2.60 – 3.39	<i>Moderately Practiced (MP)</i>						
	1.80 – 2.59	<i>Less Practiced (LP)</i>						
	1.00 – 1.79	<i>Almost Not Practiced (ANP)</i>						

Table 2.2

Level of Classroom Instructional Practices of Elementary School Teachers in terms of Learning Environment as observed by the School Heads

Indicators	Frequency					Mean	SD	DI
	5	4	3	2	1			
1. The teachers implement safety policies, guidelines, and procedures to regularly maintain a safe and secure learning environment to enhance individual and group learning.	13	5	0	0	0	4.72	0.46	HP
2. The teachers ensure that learners can articulate and adhere to the safety guidelines and practices in all the learning tasks.	10	6	2	0	0	4.44	0.70	HP
3. The teachers enhance polite and respectful interactions with learners and among learners and exhibits sensitivity to learners' differences.	10	7	1	0	0	4.50	0.62	HP
4. The teachers sustain proactive classroom structure management practices to support flexible movement of learners in all learning activities by providing optimal space and time appropriate to their needs.	7	10	1	0	0	4.33	0.59	HP
5. The teachers construct carefully structured groups in which learners are engaged in learning experiences that clearly reflect all elements of cooperative learning.	10	7	0	1	0	4.44	0.78	HP
6. The teachers provide complex tasks in which all learners share the authority of setting goals, assessing learning, and facilitating learning.	10	7	0	1	0	4.44	0.78	HP
7. The teachers are able to create a learning environment that sustains learners' active engagement and self-motivation.	10	7	1	0	0	4.50	0.62	HP
8. The teachers encourage the learners to take responsibility of their behavior.	10	8	0	0	0	4.56	0.51	HP
9. The teachers implement a well-established procedure for learners to monitor their own classroom behavior.	9	9	0	0	0	4.50	0.51	HP
10. The teachers closely monitor the learners so that misbehavior is detected early before it involves more learners or becomes a serious disruption.	9	9	0	0	0	4.50	0.51	HP
Composite Mean						4.49	0.61	HP

Legend: 4.20 – 5.00 *Highly Practiced (HP)*
 3.40 – 4.19 *Well-Practiced (WP)*
 2.60 – 3.39 *Moderately Practiced (MP)*
 1.80 – 2.59 *Less Practiced (LP)*
 1.00 – 1.79 *Almost Not Practiced (ANP)*

Table 2.3

Level of Classroom Instructional Practices of Elementary School Teachers in terms of Diversity of Learners as observed by the School Heads

Indicators	Frequency					Mean	SD	DI
	5	4	3	2	1			
1. The teachers provide differentiated and developmentally appropriate learning experiences to address the diverse individual learning needs of learners.	6	11	1	0	0	4.28	0.57	HP
2. The teachers provide appropriate instructional adaptation for diverse learners to allow them to have opportunities to actively engage in various and effective learning activities.	4	12	2	0	0	4.11	0.58	WP
3. The teachers demonstrate a wider understanding of the educability of individual learners.	4	12	2	0	0	4.11	0.58	WP
4. The teachers employ extensive repertoire of strategies to create a learner-centered environment that addresses individual and group of learners' linguistic, cultural, socio-economic, and religious backgrounds.	4	12	1	1	0	4.06	0.73	WP
5. The teachers employ extensive repertoire of strategies to create a learner-centered environment that addresses the learning needs of the individual and group of learners with special educational needs.	2	14	1	1	0	3.94	0.64	WP
6. The teachers employ extensive repertoire of strategies to create a learner-centered environment that addresses the special educational needs of the individual and group of learners in difficult circumstances.	3	10	4	1	0	3.83	0.79	WP
7. The teachers employ extensive repertoire of strategies to create a learner-centered environment that addresses the learning needs of individual and group of learners from indigenous groups.	3	11	3	1	0	3.89	0.76	WP
8. The teachers demonstrate an understanding of the purpose and value of learning about learners' background to inform instructions.	6	11	1	0	0	4.28	0.57	HP
9. The teachers demonstrate a wider understanding of a culture-based education.	5	11	2	0	0	4.17	0.62	WP
10. The teachers deliver appropriate instructional adaptation for individual learner needs to engage in various learning activities.	5	11	2	0	0	4.17	0.62	WP
	Composite Mean					4.08	0.65	WP

Legend: 4.20 – 5.00 *Highly Practiced (HP)*
 3.40 – 4.19 *Well-Practiced (WP)*
 2.60 – 3.39 *Moderately Practiced (MP)*
 1.80 – 2.59 *Less Practiced (LP)*
 1.00 – 1.79 *Almost Not Practiced (ANP)*

Table 2.4

Level of Classroom Instructional Practices of Elementary School Teachers regarding Curriculum and Planning as observed by the School Heads

Indicators	Frequency					Mean	SD	DI
	5	4	3	2	1			
1. The teachers manage well-structured lesson with emphasis on explicit connections between previous learning and new concepts and skills.	6	12	0	0	0	4.33	0.49	HP
2. The teachers' progression from the warmup to the main activity is thoughtfully planned.	6	11	1	0	0	4.28	0.57	HP
3. The teachers implement the lesson with appropriate elements of a developmentally sequenced teaching and learning processes to meet curriculum requirements and varied teaching contexts.	5	13	0	0	0	4.28	0.46	HP
4. The teachers' sequence of activities purposefully scaffolds learners toward achieving the lesson's objectives.	4	14	0	0	0	4.22	0.43	HP
5. The teachers' sequence of learning activities keeps learners engaged in the content and has a clear sense of purpose throughout the class period.	5	13	0	0	0	4.28	0.46	HP
6. The teachers integrate extensive and multidisciplinary learning resources, including ICT, which are appropriate and aligned with the learning goals.	5	11	0	1	1	4.00	1.03	WP
7. The teachers utilize a variety of instructional materials and resources that are aligned with the instructional purposes which always support the learning goals.	6	11	1	0	0	4.28	0.57	HP
8. The teachers use ICT-based interactive and transdisciplinary learning resources to increase learners' comprehension.	7	9	1	0	1	4.17	0.99	WP
9. The teachers use multidisciplinary educational materials that have been locally or indigenously adapted skillfully to captivate students' minds and deepen their learning.	5	10	2	1	0	4.06	0.80	WP
10. The teachers demonstrate new information by engaging the learners' cognitive processes.	6	9	2	1	0	4.11	0.83	WP
Composite Mean						4.20	0.66	HP

Legend: 4.20 – 5.00 *Highly Practiced (HP)*
 3.40 – 4.19 *Well-Practiced (WP)*
 2.60 – 3.39 *Moderately Practiced (MP)*
 1.80 – 2.59 *Less Practiced (LP)*
 1.00 – 1.79 *Almost Not Practiced (ANP)*

Table 2.5

Level of Classroom Instructional Practices of Elementary School Teachers regarding Assessment and Reporting as observed by the School Heads

Indicators	Frequency					Mean	SD	DI
	5	4	3	2	1			
1. The teachers integrate assessment strategies that engage learners in self- and peer-assessment.	8	9	1	0	0	4.39	0.61	HP
2. The teachers use assessment strategies which engage learners in assessment criteria to self-monitor and reflect on their own progress.	6	10	2	0	0	4.22	0.65	HP
3. The teachers prompt learners to frequently assess their own work and the work of their peers using assessment criteria embedded in teacher- or learners-generated rubrics, peer reviews, and/or reflection logs.	7	10	1	0	0	4.33	0.59	HP
4. The teachers provide assessment strategies consistent with the curriculum requirements.	8	10	0	0	0	4.44	0.51	HP
5. The teachers predominantly use assessment strategies which are embedded as an integral part of the lesson and are aligned with the intended instructional or consistent with the content standards.	6	11	1	0	0	4.28	0.57	HP
6. The teachers use assessment procedures that draw out evidence of whether learners have learned the intended learning outcomes.	7	10	1	0	0	4.33	0.59	HP
7. The teachers provide feedback that results in opportunities for all learners to improve learning and to assess their own progress and that of others.	7	11	0	0	0	4.39	0.50	HP
8. The teachers establish a routine for constructive feedbacking where learners can participate and respond productively.	6	10	2	0	0	4.22	0.65	HP
9. The teachers provide opportunities for self and peer feedbacking that is specific and is focused on advancing their learning of the lesson on hand.	5	12	1	0	0	4.22	0.55	HP
10. The teachers provide suggestions/ tasks/ activities/ clarifications, that fully guides most of the learners toward the intended learning outcomes.	7	9	2	0	0	4.28	0.67	HP
Composite Mean						4.31	0.59	HP

Legend: 4.20 – 5.00 *Highly Practiced (HP)*
 3.40 – 4.19 *Well-Practiced (WP)*
 2.60 – 3.39 *Moderately Practiced (MP)*
 1.80 – 2.59 *Less Practiced (LP)*
 1.00 – 1.79 *Almost Not Practiced (ANP)*

Table 2.6*Summary Table of Classroom Instructional Practices of Elementary School Teachers*

Skills	Composite Mean	Verbal Interpretation
Content Knowledge and Pedagogy	4.28	HP
Learning Environment	4.49	HP
Diversity of Learners	4.08	WP
Curriculum and Planning	4.20	HP
Assessment and Reporting	4.31	HP
Grand Mean	4.27	HP

Legend: 4.20 – 5.00 Highly Practiced (HP)
3.40 – 4.19 Well-Practiced (WP)
2.60 – 3.39 Moderately Practiced (MP)
1.80 – 2.59 Less Practiced (LP)
1.00 – 1.79 Almost Not Practiced (ANP)

PART III. The Significant Relationship between the Level of Instructional Supervisory Practices of School Heads and Classroom Instructional Practices of Elementary School Teachers

Table 3*The significant relationship between the level of Instructional Supervisory Practices of School Heads and Classroom Instructional Practices of Elementary School Teachers*

		Correlations		Interpretation	Decision
		ISP Mean	CIP Mean		
Spearman's rho	Correlation	1.000	.036	Not significant	Do not reject H_0
	ISP Coefficient (r)				
	Mean p-value	.	.887		
	N	214	18		
	Correlation	.036	1.000		
	CIP Coefficient (r)				
Mean p-value	.887	.			
N	18	18			

DISCUSSION

PART I. Level of the Instructional Supervisory Practices of School Heads

Table 1.1

Level of the Instructional Supervisory Practices of School Heads in Alabat Island in terms of Peer Supervision as evaluated by the elementary school teachers

Table 1.1 presents the level of the instructional supervisory practices of school heads in Alabat Island as evaluated by the elementary school teachers in terms of peer supervision. The composite mean of the indicators is 4.41, with a standard deviation of 0.67. This suggests that the school heads have demonstrated a high level of practice in these indicators.

The positive outcomes can be attributed to the motivation of school heads to attain a proficient rating in their Office Performance Review and Commitment Form (OPCRF) concerning the Key Result Area (KRA) of building connections. This KRA is associated with peer supervision because it emphasizes the promotion of an inclusive and supportive learning environment by managing diverse relationships with authorities, colleagues, parents, and stakeholders. This involves overseeing school organizations to align with institutional goals and implementing inclusive practices. Furthermore, peer supervision is essential in this area because it further enhances professional development and strengthens the interconnectedness of these efforts.

An observer could discern from the presented data that school heads highly engage in serving as resource speakers or consultants in In-Service Training (INSET), as evidenced by the highest mean score of 4.60 and a standard deviation of 0.54, indicating consistent practice. Additionally, they demonstrate a solid commitment to their professional development by regularly attending training, seminars, and workshops, as indicated by a mean score of 4.56 and a standard deviation of 0.60, also interpreted as highly practiced.

The active participation of school heads in serving as resource speaker or consultant in In-Service Training (INSET) and other professional development programs can be attributed to the consistent implementation of programs, activities, and projects (PAPs) initiated by the school division office. These initiatives offer school heads opportunities to collaborate with their peers and improve their supervisory practices through technical assistance, all aimed at enhancing teaching and learning processes.

Furthermore, they actively seek support from external organizations to benefit learners, as reflected in the mean score of 4.49 with a standard deviation of 0.63, indicating another highly practiced behavior. This behavior can be linked to the school heads' consistent implementation of the Adopt-a-School Program (ASP) within their respective schools. The ASP involves partnering with private entities to address the resource needs of public schools nationwide.

However, involvement in research plenums as panel members to provide feedback to researchers seems less frequent, having a mean score of 4.00 with a standard deviation of 0.88, suggesting a well-practiced but potentially less consistent engagement in this area. Nonetheless, this area is indicated in their Office Performance Commitment and Review Form (OPCRF) in the indicator of leading strategically to utilize relevant research findings from reliable sources in facilitating data-driven and evidence-based innovations to improve school performance. Limited contribution to this area may stem from the technical and pedagogical knowledge of school heads in writing research. Each school designates a school research coordinator responsible for conducting research, which may explain why school heads are not actively engaged.

The evaluation of instructional supervisory practices by teachers highlights the significance of peer supervision, as indicated by the highly practiced behaviors observed among school heads. The research findings underscore the importance of peer supervision in educational settings. Amanvermez et al. (2020) stress its value in personal development and professional competence, with professionals benefiting from feedback on various issues, contributing to their growth and self-awareness. Similarly, Chae (2022) underscores the benefits of peer supervision, emphasizing its role in staying informed about best practices, supporting diverse student needs, and fostering a positive professional identity among school counselors.

Table 1.2

Level of the Instructional Supervisory Practices of School heads in Alabat Island with a focus on Clinical Supervision as evaluated by elementary school teachers

Table 1.2 presents the level of instructional supervisory practices implemented by school heads in Alabat Island as evaluated by elementary school teachers with a focus on clinical supervision. The composite mean of the indicators is 4.45 with a standard deviation of 0.60, suggesting that the school heads have demonstrated a high level of practice in these indicators.

The positive outcomes can be attributed to the motivation of school heads to attain a proficient rating in their Office Performance Review and Commitment Form (OPCRF) concerning the Key Result Area (KRA) of focusing on teaching and learning. This KRA underscores the importance of assisting teachers in aligning curriculum with learner needs, integrating career awareness, and maintaining a positive environment. Also, provide technical support for teaching methods and assessment tools, using feedback to improve performance collaboratively.

One can observe from the presented data that school heads highly prioritize encouraging teachers to inquire about good practices and pursue better alternatives for teaching and learning, as evidenced by the highest mean score of 4.54 and a standard deviation of 0.58, indicating consistent practice. Additionally, they actively promote programs and projects of the Department of Education (DepEd) to enhance teaching and learning, as indicated by a mean score of 4.52 and a standard deviation of 0.59, also interpreted as highly practiced.

The consistent application of this result may be reflected in the experience and knowledge gained by the school heads from participating in District Monitoring and Evaluation Plan Adjustments (DsMEPA). This initiative aims to present school and district data, revealing the results and impacts of programs, activities, and projects, as well as identifying barriers and ongoing efforts to mitigate these issues, thereby improving the delivery of basic education services. Through their knowledge and experience, school heads may consistently encourage teachers to inquire about good practices and promote programs and projects of the Department of Education (DepEd) to enhance teaching and learning.

Furthermore, they demonstrate a solid commitment to improving classroom efficiency through observations and visitations, having a mean score of 4.51 with a standard deviation of 0.59, another highly practiced behavior.

The steadfast dedication of school heads to enhance classroom efficiency through observations and visitations may align with their Key Result Area (KRA) centered on focusing on teaching and learning. This objective aims to offer technical support to teachers regarding teaching standards and pedagogies across curriculum areas to enhance their teaching methods. The main means of verification for this objective is through consolidated classroom observation ratings, necessitating school heads to consistently conduct observations and visitations.

However, the data revealing the lowest mean score of 4.38 with a standard deviation of 0.60, for the provision of systematic assessment and constructive feedback by school heads to teachers underscores potential areas for improvement.

The level of mentoring skills and technical assistance provided by school heads could be a contributing factor. The duties and responsibilities outlined by the Department of Education and Civil Service Commission shed light on expectations for school heads in this regard. School heads are expected to mentor teachers facing content and skills difficulties, provide technical assistance to enhance competencies, ensure instructional material quality, and review teachers' lesson plans for improvement.

The evaluation of instructional supervisory practices by teachers indicates that school heads highly prioritize clinical supervision, reflecting a commitment to enhancing teacher professionalism. Wardhani (2021) underscores the importance of clinical supervision, emphasizing its role in identifying and addressing weaknesses in teacher professionalism. Supervisors engage in direct interactions and observations to assess teaching processes and to promote both student learning outcomes and the professional development of teachers. Principals actively support teachers' professionalism by conducting classroom visits, engaging in private discussions, and encouraging participation in relevant training opportunities.

Table 1.3

Level of the Instructional Supervisory Practices of School heads in Alabat Island in terms of Developmental Supervision as evaluated by the elementary school teachers

Table 1.3 displays the instructional supervisory practices implemented by school heads in Alabat Island, as evaluated by elementary school teachers in the context of developmental supervision. The composite mean of the indicators is 4.50 with a standard deviation of 0.60, indicating that the school heads highly practiced these indicators.

The positive outcomes can be attributed to the motivation of school heads to attain a proficient rating in their Office Performance Review and Commitment Form (OPCRF) concerning the Key Result Area (KRA) of developing self and others. This KRA underscores the importance of aligning personal and professional goals with Philippine Professional Standards, actively participating in professional networks to enhance skills, and initiating development programs aimed at enhancing school personnel's performance.

From the presented data, one can observe that school heads highly prioritize encouraging teachers' participation in developmental programs such as In-Service Training (INSET), seminars, and workshops to improve classroom instructional practices. The significance of this finding is supported by the highest mean score of 4.63 with a standard deviation of 0.52, indicating consistent practice. Additionally, they rigorously adhere to DepEd Orders/Memoranda aimed at teacher development, as reflected in a mean score of 4.58 and a standard deviation of 0.64, also interpreted as highly practiced.

The consistent encouragement of school heads for teachers to participate in developmental programs may be reflected in their strict adherence to policies such as Republic Act No. 10912, also known as the "Continuing Professional Development (CPD) Act of 2016." CPD is mandatory for the renewal of the Professional Identification Card of all registered and licensed professionals under the regulation of the PRC.

Furthermore, they actively incorporate developmental programs into the School Improvement Plan (SIP) to foster lifelong learning among teachers, with a mean score of 4.53 and a standard deviation of 0.58, indicating another highly practiced behavior.

The incorporation of developmental programs into the School Improvement Plan (SIP) may be associated with the consistent adherence of school heads to DepEd Order No. 44 s. 2015, which stipulates that the implementation of development activities integral to it occurs in the school, such as projects under the Continuous Improvement Program (CIP) and the creation and mobilization of Learning Action Cells (LACs). It also emphasizes that the training design and learning package should adhere to the training program standards set by the National Educators Academy of the Philippines (NEAP) to ensure the quality of developmental programs for teachers.

However, the data showing the lowest mean score of 4.44 with regards to the practice of school heads in diagnosing developmental levels, expertise, commitment, and

educational situations of teachers, as well as selecting interpersonal approaches that create the best supervision match, and using observation data to identify learning gaps for developing teacher interventions, highlights potential areas for improvement.

The results may be due to the lack of a clear framework or guidelines for school heads in assessing the developmental levels, expertise, commitment, and educational situations of teachers. Thus, school heads may struggle to perform accurate evaluations. Similarly, if there are no standardized procedures for selecting interpersonal approaches or utilizing observation data, inconsistencies in supervision practices may arise.

Overall, the evaluation of instructional supervisory practices by teachers suggests that school heads prioritize developmental supervision, demonstrating their commitment to supporting teachers' growth and development. These findings align with those of Anidjar et al. (2023), who noted that supervisors employing the developmental supervision model recognize teachers as individuals at varying stages of development. Developmental supervision offers flexibility and adaptability to tailor support based on individual circumstances, facilitating efficient decision-making and timely adjustments. Matsko (2020) corroborates this assertion by highlighting the use of ongoing formative assessment in developmental supervision to help teachers acknowledge and enhance their strengths while identifying areas for improvement.

Table 1.4

Level of the Instructional Supervisory Practices Implemented by School heads in Alabat Island in terms of Differentiated Supervision as evaluated by elementary school teachers

Table 1.4 presents the level of instructional supervisory practices implemented by school heads in Alabat Island, as evaluated by elementary school teachers, with a focus on differentiated supervision. The composite mean of the indicators is 4.44 with a standard deviation of 0.59, indicating that the school heads have demonstrated a high level of practice.

The commitment of school heads to address the individual needs of teachers may contribute to positive outcomes, as evidenced by results from the Self-Assessment Tool (SAT), Individual Performance Commitment and Review Form - Development Plans (IPCRF-DP), and feedback from peers. School heads can use this feedback and results as a basis to address the individual needs of teachers and ultimately improve the teaching and learning process.

Analysis of the presented data reveals that school heads prioritize involving teachers in planning, designing, and evaluating individual professional development programs. This is evidenced by the highest mean score of 4.50 and a standard deviation of 0.58, indicating consistent practice. Additionally, they actively involve teachers in evaluations, staff development, and informal observations to enhance classroom instructional practices, as reflected in a mean score of 4.48 and a standard deviation of 0.53, also interpreted as highly practiced.

The involvement of teachers in these activities may indicate the school heads' aim to obtain additional Means of Verification (MOVs) for inclusion in the Office Performance Commitment and Review Form (OPCRF) for school heads and the Individual Performance Commitment and Review Form (IPCRF) for teachers. According to DepEd Order No. 44 s. 2015, the participation and involvement of school heads, teachers, and staff in planning and implementing developmental programs may be integrated into the Results-Based Performance Management System (RPMS) as performance objectives within corresponding Key Result Areas. These objectives can be included in either the IPCRF for teachers and staff or the OPCRf for school heads.

Furthermore, they diligently prepare instructional supervision plans and consider the results of the Self-Assessment Tool (SAT) when crafting these plans. Both ranked third with mean scores of 4.46 and standard deviations of 0.60 and 0.62, respectively, indicating another highly practiced behavior.

The consistent preparation of instructional supervisory plans by school heads, which consider the results of teachers' Self-Assessment Tool (SAT), may stem from their aspiration to achieve a proficient rating in the Key Result Area of Focusing on Teaching and Learning. One of the objectives of this KRA aims to assist teachers in reviewing, contextualizing, and implementing learning standards to ensure the curriculum's relevance for learners. The primary Means of Verification (MOVs) for this objective is the Instructional Supervisory Plan (ISP), which school heads often utilize by incorporating teachers' SAT results into its formulation.

However, the data showing the lowest mean score of 4.39 highlights potential areas for improvement regarding the practice of school heads in using different approaches and allots one on one consultation in addressing teacher's individual problems or needs.

The result may be attributed to time constraints and lack of training. School heads may face limited time available for one-on-one consultations due to their numerous responsibilities. Also, they may not have received sufficient training on how to use different approaches.

Overall, the assessment of instructional supervisory practices by teachers suggests a strong emphasis on differentiated supervision by school heads. This approach, endorsed by Mausbach and Morrison (2022), aims to enhance the overall system while meeting the diverse needs of teaching staff. Differentiated supervision moves beyond isolated practices, offering a comprehensive model that fosters a culture of support for individuals, small groups, and the entire school community. It emphasizes the implementation of high-leverage strategies to enhance student learning and ensures a targeted focus on improvement across all levels of the educational system.

Table 1.5

Summary Table of the Instructional Supervisory Practices Implemented by School Heads

Table 1.5 provides a summary of the instructional supervisory practices implemented by school heads, including peer supervision, clinical supervision, developmental supervision, and differentiated supervision, as evaluated by the elementary school teachers. The grand mean of the indicators is 4.45, suggesting that the school heads have demonstrated a high level of practice in these indicators.

The high levels of supervisory practices of school heads, as evidenced by their emphasis on instructional supervision, could be seen as part of their efforts to align with the standards set by the Results-based Performance Management System (RPMS), as outlined in DepEd Order No. 2, s. 2015. This system directs school heads to integrate instructional supervisory practices into their routines, ensuring adherence to departmental performance assessment and improvement guidelines (Tansiongco and Ibarra, 2020).

However, peer supervision obtained the lowest mean, indicating a significant gap in its effectiveness. This underscores the urgent need to improve the practice, emphasizing the importance of implementing changes or introducing new strategies to enhance peer supervision and ensure it serves its intended purpose more effectively.

PART II. Level of Classroom Instructional Practices of Elementary School Teachers

Table 2.1

Level of Classroom Instructional Practices of Elementary School Teachers in terms of Content Knowledge and Pedagogy as observed by the School Heads

Table 2.1 presents the level of classroom instructional practices of elementary school teachers as observed by the school heads in terms of content knowledge and pedagogy. The composite mean of the indicators is 4.28 with a standard deviation of 0.70, indicating a high level of practice by the teachers in these indicators.

Teachers' high level of practice in terms of content knowledge and pedagogy may be attributed to the constant support provided by the Department of Education through timely, appropriate, and necessary training and seminars. These initiatives aim to enhance the teaching and learning process, keep educators updated on modern instructional methods, and enable them to effectively engage with 21st-century learners. The presented data shows that teachers highly prioritize establishing classroom practices fostering open communication between teachers and learners, as well as among peers, with the highest mean score of 4.39 and a standard deviation of 0.50, indicating consistent practice.

The prioritization of establishing classroom practices that foster open communication between teachers and learners, as well as among peers may be associated with the constant adherence of teachers in the K-12 curriculum framework

which stipulates that it is designed to be collaborative and student-centered. It emphasizes active participation, interaction, and collaboration among students, as well as between students and teachers. The curriculum framework encourages student engagement through various collaborative learning activities, group projects, and discussions.

Additionally, teachers exhibit a significant focus on fostering intra- and interdisciplinary content relationships, along with utilizing activities to enhance learners' literacy and numeracy skills. Both aspects achieved a mean score of 4.33 and a standard deviation of 0.59, indicating a high level of practice.

The integration of disciplines within and across subject areas may be associated with the constant adherence of teachers in the K-12 curriculum. The curriculum emphasizes the interconnectedness of knowledge and the importance of providing students with opportunities to make connections between different subjects. This approach aims to promote a holistic understanding of concepts and develop students' critical thinking skills by allowing them to see how various disciplines relate to each other in real-world contexts.

Furthermore, they exhibit extensive knowledge beyond their specialization, motivate learners to explore topics, provide opportunities for comparing and contrasting ideas, synthesize information, and employ communication strategies effectively, all ranked third having a mean score of 4.28 with a standard deviation of 0.75, indicating another highly practiced set of behaviors.

The results may be linked to the significant influence of a constructivist classroom on teachers. Teachers who motivate learners to explore topics, offer opportunities for comparing and contrasting ideas and synthesize information actively facilitate the construction of knowledge by students.

However, responsible use of online and multimedia platforms demonstrated through applying digital etiquette and responsible social interaction, seems slightly less frequent, though still well-practiced, having a mean score of 4.11 with a standard deviation of 0.96.

The results may be linked to the limited integration of Information and Communication Technology (ICT) skills across subject areas within the K-12 curriculum. Currently, ICT is primarily addressed in a single quarter, alongside Entrepreneurship, under the subject of EPP (Edukasyong Pantahanan at Pangkabuhayan). Consequently, the emphasis on developing ICT competencies is reduced, as it receives less instructional time and attention compared to other subjects. This fragmented approach to ICT instruction may contribute to students' limited proficiency in utilizing technology effectively across various academic disciplines.

The school heads' observations imply that teachers' instructional practices regarding content knowledge and pedagogy are highly practiced. This assertion is

supported by the findings of Nkundabakura et al. (2023), who highlight the importance of teachers continuously updating their subject content knowledge, pedagogy, and technological skills to enhance their effectiveness in teaching. Additionally, Neuman and Danielson (2021) emphasize that teachers who possess higher levels of content and pedagogical knowledge are more successful in implementing the curriculum with integrity. Overall, these insights underscore the significance of ongoing professional development in improving teaching practices and benefiting student learning outcomes.

Table 2.2

Level of Classroom Instructional Practices of Elementary School Teachers in terms of Learning Environment as observed by the School Heads

Table 2.2 presents the level of classroom instructional practices of elementary school teachers as observed by the school heads in terms of learning environment. The composite mean of the indicators is 4.49, with a standard deviation of 0.61. This suggests that the teachers have practiced these indicators at a high level.

The results may stem from the rigorous implementation of the Child-Friendly School System (CFSS) at elementary and secondary education levels. CFSS fosters a democratic environment based on children's rights, ensuring the acceptance of all students and organizing teaching-learning processes according to their interests and needs. It prioritizes health, safety, and protection measures for students, to eliminate gender-based discrimination. The overarching goals of CFSS include providing a healthy, hygienic, and safe learning environment equipped with adequate water and sanitation facilities, promoting healthy policies and practices, and ensuring access to sufficient sports equipment for physical activities.

From the data presented, it is evident that school heads perceive teachers' implementation of safety policies and procedures, as well as fostering learners' responsibility for their behavior, as highly practiced. This is indicated by mean scores of 4.72 and 4.56, respectively indicating consistent practice.

The results can be attributed to the implementation of Disaster Risk Reduction Management (DRRM) in schools. DRRM empowers school offices, teachers, students, and stakeholders to actively participate in maintaining a safe educational environment conducive to effective learning. Through DRRM initiatives, schools prioritize activities such as risk assessment, hazard mitigation, and emergency preparedness, fostering a culture of safety and responsibility among all members of the school community. Consequently, teachers are more inclined to adhere to safety protocols, and learners are encouraged to take ownership of their behavior, thereby contributing to a secure and conducive learning environment.

Additionally, teachers demonstrate high proficiency in enhancing polite and respectful interactions among learners, maintaining active engagement and self-motivation, and implementing procedures for learners to monitor their behavior. These aspects all achieved mean scores of 4.50, indicating consistent practice.

The proficiency demonstrated by teachers can be attributed to the implementation of the DepEd Child Protection Policy. This policy mandates concerned individuals to adhere to guidelines aimed at protecting school children against abuse, violence, exploitation, discrimination, bullying, and other forms of harm. By adhering to the provisions outlined in the policy, teachers acquire the knowledge and tools necessary to create a safe and supportive learning environment where positive interactions thrive. This fosters a culture of mutual respect, active engagement, and self-awareness among learners, thereby contributing to their overall well-being and academic success.

Moreover, closely monitoring learners to detect misbehavior early is also highly practiced, with a mean score of 4.50 indicating consistency. The result can be attributed to the influence of behaviorism and social learning theory on teachers. Behaviorism emphasizes observable behaviors and employs reinforcement and punishment to shape behavior. Teachers closely monitor learners, identifying misbehavior and applying appropriate consequences or interventions to promote positive behavior. Social learning theory posits that individuals acquire knowledge and behaviors by observing others and the outcomes of their actions. Teachers can model and reinforce positive behaviors, addressing and correcting misbehavior before it escalates.

However, the data showing the lowest mean score of 4.33 highlights potential areas for improvement regarding the practice of teachers in sustaining proactive classroom structure management practices to support the flexible movement of learners in all learning activities by providing optimal space and time appropriate to their needs.

The result may be attributed to teachers' non-compliance with DepEd Order No. 21 s. 2023 titled "Brigada Eskwela Implementing Guidelines". The policy expressly mandates that schools must maintain cleanliness and devoid unnecessary artwork, decorations, tarpaulins, and posters on school grounds, in classrooms, and throughout all school facilities at all times.

Overall, this implies that school heads observations on teachers' instructional practices related to creating a conducive learning environment as highly effective. This is supported by Munir et al. (2021), who found that an improved learning environment correlates with enhanced student performance.

Additionally, Prashanti and Ramnarayan (2020) highlight the significant influence of the learning environment on students' learning capabilities, emphasizing that safety and comfort are paramount, regardless of technological advancements or teaching methods. They assert that the learning environment plays a crucial role in the overall development of students, as it cannot be replaced by even the most advanced pedagogical tools or technologies. This underscores the importance of teachers in collaboratively establishing an environment that nurtures learning and development for all students.

Table 2.3

Level of Classroom Instructional Practices of Elementary School Teachers in terms of Diversity of Learners as observed by the School Heads

Table 2.3 presents the level of classroom instructional practices of elementary school teachers as observed by the school heads in terms of the diversity of learners. The composite mean of the indicators is 4.08 with a standard deviation of 0.65 which implies that the teachers well-practiced these indicators.

The results can be attributed to time constraints in teaching with regard to the diversity of learners. Preparing diverse teaching instructions and materials to cater to the needs of all learners is crucial for effective classroom instruction. However, this process can be time-consuming for teachers. Adapting lessons, creating alternative assignments, and gathering resources tailored to individual students or groups requires significant effort outside regular class hours. Despite their best efforts, time constraints may limit the depth and breadth of instructional differentiation, impacting the extent to which teachers can fully meet the diverse learning needs of their students.

The data indicates that school heads perceive teachers' instructional practices as well-practiced, as reflected by the mean scores of 3.83 and 3.94 for the respective indicators. These indicators highlight the extent to which teachers employ diverse strategies to create learner-centered environments tailored to the needs of both individuals and groups of students, particularly those with special educational needs and those facing challenging circumstances.

The results might stem from teachers' lower prioritization of inclusive education, possibly because of limited awareness or understanding of its significance. Although the Department of Education (DepEd) is committed to providing quality education for all Filipino citizens through the K to 12 Basic Education Program, which includes a focus on inclusive education, there may be gaps in ensuring that teachers prioritize and fully implement inclusive practices in their classrooms.

Additionally, teachers are employing a diverse range of strategies to create a learner-centered environment catering to the needs of individual and group learners from indigenous backgrounds, with a mean score of 3.89 and standard deviations suggesting well-practiced behaviors.

The results could be attributed to the low prioritization of teachers in the Department of Education's (DepEd) Indigenous People's Education Program (IPEd). This may stem from the fact that only a few indigenous learners are enrolled in public schools nationwide. Nevertheless, DepEd continues its efforts through IPEd, which aims to integrate indigenous knowledge, models, methods, and content into both formal and non-formal educational systems. The program's objective is to impart basic educational knowledge, skills, and values to ethnic groups while preserving their cultural identity.

Delving deeper into the table, the data indicates that teachers do not extensively utilize a diverse range of strategies to create a learner-centered environment that addresses individual and group learners' linguistic, cultural, socio-economic, and religious backgrounds. Despite this, they still receive a mean score of 4.06, suggesting well-practiced behaviors. Similarly, teachers do not highly demonstrate a comprehensive understanding of the educability of individual learners, as evidenced by their mean score of 4.11. Additionally, teachers do not highly provide appropriate instructional adaptations for diverse learners to actively engage in various and effective learning activities, yet they still receive a mean score of 4.11.

These findings suggest a notable gap between the perception of highly practiced instructional practices and their actual implementation. The results could be attributed to the training received by teachers concerning learner diversity. Based on the Department of Education's Basic Education Information System (BEIS), the majority of teachers have not received training regarding the diversity of learners. This highlights a need for improvement to ensure that teachers consistently address the diverse needs of their students through tailored instructional approaches.

Moreover, the data suggests that teachers do not extensively demonstrate a deep understanding of culture-based education, as reflected by the mean score of 4.17 for this indicator. Similarly, teachers do not highly provide appropriate instructional adaptations to meet the individual needs of learners, enabling them to engage effectively in various learning activities, as evidenced by another mean score of 4.17.

These findings indicate a gap between the desired level of proficiency in understanding culture-based education and the delivery of tailored instructional adaptations. The results may be due to limited resources or support available within the educational system to assist teachers in integrating cultural perspectives into their teaching practices and addressing the individual needs of diverse learners.

Overall, the school heads' observations imply that teachers' instructional practices regarding diversity of learners are well-practiced. Levy-Feldman and Libman (2022) emphasized that in today's multicultural landscape, educators must prioritize these practices further to ensure all students develop 21st-century skills while fostering an inclusive, intercultural classroom environment.

Table 2.4

Level of Classroom Instructional Practices of Elementary School Teachers regarding Curriculum and Planning as observed by the School Heads

Table 2.4 presents the level of classroom instructional practices of elementary school teachers as observed by the school heads in terms of curriculum and planning. The composite mean of the indicators is 4.20 with a standard deviation of 0.66, which implies that the teachers highly practiced these indicators.

The observed result may be attributed to legal mandates such as the K to 12 Basic Education Program in the Philippines. This program emphasizes learner-centered approaches, competency-based education, and the integration of 21st-century skills into the curriculum, including learning and innovation skills, information, media, and technology skills, and life and career skills. These elements are reflected in the indicators observed by school heads in terms of curriculum and planning. Thus, teachers who adhere to the K to 12 curriculum frameworks are likely to prioritize effective curriculum planning and implementation to align with the program's goals and standards.

The data presented show that teachers in this study demonstrate substantial competency in structuring lessons effectively, emphasizing explicit connections between past learning and new concepts and skills. This is supported by the highest mean score of 4.33, indicating a highly practiced approach. Following closely behind are indicators related to thoughtful progression from warm-up to main activity, utilization of diverse instructional materials aligned with learning goals, and implementation of developmentally sequenced teaching and learning processes, all of which received high mean scores of 4.28.

The results may be influenced by the principles of constructivist learning theory embraced by teachers. According to this theory, learners construct their understanding of new concepts based on prior knowledge and experiences. By emphasizing explicit connections between past and new learning, teachers facilitate the construction of meaningful understanding among students, fostering deeper learning and retention of knowledge. Additionally, the results may reflect teachers' adherence to the K to 12 curriculum frameworks. These standards emphasize the importance of effective lesson structuring, alignment with learning goals, and the use of diverse instructional materials to support student learning and achievement.

However, the data suggests that teachers do not extensively integrate a wide range of learning resources, including ICT, that are both appropriate and aligned with the learning goals, as reflected by the mean score of 4.00 for this indicator. Similarly, teachers do not highly utilize ICT-based interactive and transdisciplinary learning resources to enhance learners' comprehension, as evidenced by another mean score of 4.17.

The results may indicate a lack of learning resources, including ICT, in the classroom. Many classrooms in the Philippines do not have sufficient ICT resources to meet the needs of all students. Despite efforts by the DepEd Computerization program to improve computer literacy among school personnel and address issues with using ICT equipment, it may be concluded that the program is not fully implemented due to inadequate equipment, insufficient training for implementers, and a lack of community knowledge about ICT. As a result, there is a deficiency in integrating ICT resources into the teaching and learning process.

Additionally, the use of teachers' multidisciplinary educational materials that have been locally or indigenously adapted skillfully to captivate students' minds and deepen their learning, obtained a mean of 4.06 which can be interpreted as well-practiced.

The results could be due to time constraints, which limit teachers' ability to prioritize the localization and enhancement of educational materials. With demanding schedules and numerous responsibilities, including lesson planning and other ancillary works, teachers may struggle to allocate sufficient time for adapting materials to the specific needs of their students.

Additionally, the process of localization and enhancement requires extensive research and creativity, which can be challenging to achieve within limited time constraints. Thus, the result suggests that while this aspect of teaching is not practiced as highly as others, there is still a noticeable level of proficiency.

Furthermore, the data suggests that teachers do not extensively demonstrate new information by actively engaging learners' cognitive processes, as indicated by the mean score of 4.11 for this indicator. Similarly, teachers do not highly utilize multidisciplinary educational materials that have been skillfully adapted locally or indigenously to captivate students' minds and deepen their learning, supported by a mean score of 4.06.

The results could be due to a lack of awareness or training on innovative teaching strategies that foster cognitive engagement, alongside limited access to locally adapted educational resources. This is evident in the available resources on the Learning Resource Management & Development System (LRMDS).

Overall, the school heads' observations imply that teachers' instructional practices regarding curriculum and planning are highly practiced. The study of Nogueira (2020) corroborated this assertion by concluding that evidence on curriculum, evident both in theory and pedagogical practice, prompts us to reconsider curricula as more than mere content to be imparted to students. Instead, they should be deliberated upon to address the genuine needs of all stakeholders within the school environment. Consequently, curriculum and planning must remain interconnected, facilitating a cycle of action-reflection-action to ensure the success of the intended process and, ultimately, prioritize student learning with utmost significance.

Table 2.5

Level of Classroom Instructional Practices of Elementary School Teachers regarding Assessment and Reporting as observed by the School Heads

Table 2.5 presents the level of classroom instructional practices of elementary school teachers as observed by the school heads in terms of assessment and reporting. The composite mean of the indicators is 4.31 with a standard deviation of 0.59, indicating that the teachers highly practiced these indicators.

The results may be attributed to the adherence of teachers within the policy guidelines on classroom assessment for the K to 12 Basic Education Program (BEP) of the Department of Education (DepEd). This framework recognizes the importance of assessment in measuring learners' abilities and fostering their responsibility for learning. By aligning assessment practices with curriculum standards and guidelines, teachers

ensure that assessment methods support the development of higher-order thinking and 21st-century skills among students. Moreover, the emphasis on both formative and summative assessment types enables teachers to gauge student progress effectively and provide timely feedback, aligning to help students meet learning standards and develop essential competencies outlined in the curriculum.

The data presented reveals that teachers demonstrate exemplary proficiency in aligning assessment strategies with curriculum requirements, as indicated by the highest mean score of 4.44. Additionally, teachers exhibit strong practices in engaging learners in self- and peer-assessment, while providing constructive feedback conducive to learning improvement, as evidenced by mean scores of 4.39 for both indicators.

The results may be associated with the adherence of teachers to the principles of formative assessment and learner-centered instruction. Formative assessment gathers evidence of student learning to inform teaching and enhance learning. By aligning assessment with curriculum requirements, teachers monitor progress and adapt instruction to meet individual needs, promoting student growth. Moreover, the practice of engaging learners in self- and peer-assessment, along with providing constructive feedback, aligns with the principles of learner-centered instruction, which prioritize active student involvement in the learning process and foster a supportive and collaborative learning environment.

Overall, the school heads' observations imply that teachers' instructional practices regarding assessment and reporting are highly proficient. Almasa (2020) supports this assertion by emphasizing the importance of teachers using a variety of assessment tools and strategies to monitor, evaluate, document, and report on learners' needs, progress, and achievements. Moreover, teachers are encouraged to utilize assessment data in multifaceted ways to inform and enrich the teaching and learning process. This involves offering learners constructive feedback on learning outcomes. This not only informs the reporting cycle but also enables teachers to strategically choose, organize, and use effective assessment methods.

Table 2.6

Summary Table of Classroom Instructional Practices of Elementary School Teachers

Table 2.6 presents the summary table of the instructional practices of elementary school teachers in terms of content knowledge, pedagogy, learning environment, diversity of learners, curriculum, planning, assessment, and reporting as observed by the school heads. The grand mean of the indicators is 4.27 which implies that the teachers highly practiced these indicators.

The proficient practice of teachers in terms of content knowledge and pedagogy, learning environment, curriculum and planning, assessment and reporting may be due to the programs provided by the Department of Education (DepEd) which inculcates the development and enhancement of classroom instructional practices of teachers.

Moreover, the programs, activities, and projects (PAPs) of DepEd provide support to effectively implement innovations in the teaching and learning process.

Thus, one can infer, as reflected in the study of Cayubit (2022), wherein the results have shown that there is no doubt that students' learning environment, academic motivation, learning strategies, and level of engagement are factors in their academic success. Educational psychologists, school psychologists, counselors, school administrators, teachers, and other education stakeholders can utilize the understanding of how these factors are interrelated and impact each other to inform policymaking. This can aid in shaping a conducive learning environment for students.

However, the diversity of learners obtained the lowest mean, which is verbally interpreted as well-practiced. The result may be due to a lack of awareness or understanding among teachers regarding the importance of accommodating diverse learning needs. Additionally, limited resources or training opportunities focused on inclusive practices may contribute to this outcome. Therefore, further professional development and support tailored to addressing learner diversity could be necessary to improve instructional practices in this area.

Similarly, Djurayeva and Djuraev (2024) emphasized that teachers face classroom challenges that impede the promotion of learner diversity regarding instructional practices. Additionally, they stressed that diverse learners encounter challenges in the classroom, such as language barriers, which hinder their participation and engagement. Cultural awareness is crucial in fostering an inclusive environment, as ignoring cultural differences can lead to misunderstandings. Moreover, unequal access to resources, particularly for students from disadvantaged backgrounds, restricts their academic opportunities. To tackle these challenges, educators can provide language support, undergo intercultural competence training, advocate for equal access to resources, and deliver individualized instruction tailored to each student's needs.

PART III. The Significant Relationship between the Level of Instructional Supervisory Practices of School Heads and Classroom Instructional Practices of Elementary School Teachers

Table 3

The significant relationship between the level of Instructional Supervisory Practices of School Heads and Classroom Instructional Practices of Elementary School Teachers

Table 3 indicates that there is no statistically significant relationship between the instructional supervisory practices of school heads and the classroom instructional practices of elementary school teachers ($p = .887, > 0.05$). The lack of significant difference suggests that the two variables are not associated. Additionally, the computed r -value of .036 suggests a negligible relationship between the variables.

The result indicates that there is no significant relationship between the level of instructional supervisory practices of school heads and the level of classroom instructional practices of elementary school teachers. This lack of correlation may stem from the individual goals and priorities of both school heads and teachers. School heads may aim to achieve a proficient rating in their Office Performance Commitment and Review Form (OPCRF), while teachers may strive to enhance their classroom instructional practices or achieve a proficient rating in their Individual Performance Commitment and Review Form (IPCRF). Although both parties benefit from their respective practices, there is no significant relationship between them that could contribute to their overall effectiveness.

This aligns with the findings of the study conducted by Ordanel and Dioso (2023) who found that there is no significant correlation between the level of supervisory practices of school principals and the working performance of teachers. These results indicate that teachers are effective and efficient in their roles, regardless of the leadership abilities of their principals. This suggests that teachers remain committed and dedicated to their work, even if the performance of their principals is lacking. While there may be instances where exemplary principals lead exemplary teachers, and underperforming principals lead disengaged teachers, this study reveals that both teachers and principals are performing well overall. However, it is important to note that no significant relationship was established between the two variables.

Additionally, the study by Yego et al. (2020), added that teachers' performance was not significantly influenced by the principals' instructional supervision in lesson preparation, preparation of assessment materials, lesson implementation, and innovation and creativity in teaching.

PART IV. Proposed Capacity-Building Program

Drawing from the study's findings, the researcher devised a capacity-building program titled "Empowering Educators: Strengthening Instructional Supervision through Peer Collaboration and Enhancing Classroom Practices for Diverse Learners". This program aims to enhance the instructional supervisory practices of school heads and the classroom instructional practices of elementary school teachers, with a specific focus on peer supervision and catering to the needs of diverse learners.

The program comprises several components targeting specific areas identified for improvement. Firstly, workshops and training sessions will enhance school heads' skills in peer supervision, focusing on effective observation techniques, providing constructive feedback, facilitating professional dialogue among teachers, and implementing action plans for instructional improvement. This aims to foster collaborative learning among school heads. Additionally, professional development workshops tailored to teachers' needs will cover topics such as differentiated instruction, culturally responsive teaching practices, classroom management strategies, and assessment techniques for diverse learners.

Regular collaborative planning sessions will be organized for school heads and teachers to discuss instructional goals, share best practices, and develop action plans for improvement. The program will establish mechanisms for monitoring and evaluating its effectiveness through classroom observations, participant feedback surveys, and assessments of student learning outcomes. Feedback and data analysis will guide program adjustments to ensure ongoing improvement. Further details regarding the proposed capacity-building program can be found in Appendix A.

Conclusions

Based on the summarized findings, the researcher concluded the following:

1. The findings indicate that school heads have highly practiced instructional supervisory practices. This is evidenced by their proficiency in indicators such as peer supervision, clinical supervision, developmental supervision, and differentiated supervision. However, it's noteworthy that peer supervision, while still recognized as highly practiced, achieved the lowest mean among these indicators. Therefore, there is a need to emphasize peer supervision to further enhance school heads' instructional supervisory practices. In summary, the findings suggest that school heads excel in various supervisory techniques, with room for improvement specifically in peer supervision to improve the learning environment and quality of instruction in the classrooms.
2. The findings demonstrate that elementary school teachers have highly practiced classroom instructional practices. They exhibit significant proficiency across various indicators including content knowledge and pedagogy, learning environment, curriculum planning, assessment, and reporting. The researcher concludes that teachers possess a robust repertoire of classroom instructional practices that they adeptly utilize to meet learners' needs and achieve educational objectives. However, the domain of classroom instructional practices related to diverse learners received the lowest mean score, indicating a need for improvement. Therefore, there is a pressing need to enhance this area to further empower teachers in effectively addressing the diverse needs of students.
3. The null hypothesis is accepted, indicating that there is no significant relationship between the instructional supervisory practices implemented by school heads and the classroom instructional practices of elementary school teachers. Consequently, it suggests that these two variables are not associated.
4. The researcher developed a capacity-building program aimed at enhancing the capabilities of school heads in peer supervision and equipping elementary school teachers with the skills to create a responsive learning environment that accommodates learner diversity.

Recommendations

Drawing upon the conclusions reached, the researcher delineates the subsequent recommendations:

For the DepEd Officials and Authorities

- Allocate resources and funding for professional development programs aimed at improving teachers' capacity to effectively address learner diversity.
- Implement policies that promote collaborative efforts between school heads and teachers to address instructional needs, particularly in areas related to learner diversity.
- Regularly conduct assessments and evaluations to oversee the effectiveness of instructional practices and supervisory methods at the school level.

For the District Supervisors

- Facilitate workshops and training sessions for school heads and teachers to enhance their skills in addressing the diverse needs of students in the classroom.
- Encourage a collaborative culture and perpetual enhancement by advocating for peer learning and the exchange of best practices among educators district-wide.

For the School Heads

- Establish a nurturing and inclusive school atmosphere wherein educators feel empowered to explore innovative instructional approaches tailored to the diverse needs of learners.
- Collaborate with district supervisors and fellow school leaders to exchange insights and strategies for enhancing instructional effectiveness and promoting student success.

For the Teachers

- Engage in professional development opportunities to enhance their understanding and implementation of inclusive instructional practices that address learner diversity.

- Regularly assess student needs and adjust instructional approaches to ensure that all learners receive equitable opportunities for learning and growth.
- Cultivate a welcoming and inclusive classroom atmosphere that prioritizes students' sense of value, respect, and support throughout their academic endeavors.

For the Future Researchers

- Explore the underlying factors contributing to the disparity in instructional practices related to learner diversity among teachers and develop targeted interventions to address these challenges.
- Conduct longitudinal studies to examine the long-term impact of instructional supervisory practices on teacher effectiveness and student outcomes across diverse educational settings.
- Examine how contextual elements like school culture and community dynamics influence instructional methods and supervisory interactions within educational settings.
- Include secondary teachers in the next study to enhance understanding of instructional practices and supervision dynamics across various educational levels.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

Conducting research demands dedication, time, and a systematic approach. This study focuses on evaluating instructional supervisory practices of school heads and classroom instructional practices of elementary school teachers in Alabat Island, involving human respondents. To uphold the privacy and security of participants, several considerations are paramount. Confidentiality, consent, and data protection must be meticulously addressed to anticipate any potential issues.

Throughout the research process, questionnaires will be crafted clearly and concisely to mitigate confusion. Adequate time will be given to respondents for thoughtful responses, ensuring accuracy and minimizing errors. Participants will be provided with a waiver guaranteeing the confidentiality of identities and any sensitive information participants choose not to disclose. The researcher will actively ask for cooperation, assuring participants that all collected data will be treated with utmost confidentiality, fostering trust between researcher and participant.

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